

Radiopurity and Cleanliness Challenges for the XLZD Experiment

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Leading Dark Matter (DM) technology above a -few GeV

ZEPLIN-III/XENON10

12 kg (7 kg)

2008

XENON100

62 kg (34 kg)

2013

LUX

250 kg (100 kg)

2016

PANDAX-II

580 kg (362 kg)

2017

XENON1T

2,000 kg (1,042 kg)

2018

PANDAX-4t/LUX-ZEPLIN/XENON-nT

7,000 kg (5,600 kg)

The XLZD detector concept

- Builds on mature technology → combines best of XENON and LUX-ZEPLIN
- ~factor 2 linear scale-up → manageable technical challenges
- Eventual 60-80 tonne active natural LXe target
- Two arrays 3" low-background PMTs (2362 tubes total)
 - Other sensors under study
- Drift field 240-290 V/cm
- Highly (VUV) reflective PTFE walls
- Radiopure material selection and background mitigation (active veto, online reduction, analysis)

XLZD Design book: [arxiv/2410.17137](https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.17137) (2025)

A Dark Matter and Rare Event Physics Observatory

Ultra-low BG + large exposure + high dynamic range → broad physics programme

Dark Matter:

- WIMP
- Sub-GeV
- Inelastic
- Axion-like particles
- Planck mass
- Dark photons

Neutrino nature:

- Neutrinoless double beta decay
- Neutrino magnetic moment
- Double electron capture

Supernovae:

- Early alert
- Supernova neutrinos
- Multi-messenger astrophysics

Solar:

- pp neutrinos
- Solar metallicity
- ${}^7\text{Be}$, ${}^8\text{B}$, hep

Whitepaper: LXe observatory for DM and ν -physics

[J Aalbers et al 2023 J. Phys. G: Nucl. Part. Phys. 50 013001](#)

Dark Matter discovery to the ν -fog

Neutrinoless double beta decay with ^{136}Xe

^{214}Bi γ -rays from detector materials

- Natural abundance of ^{136}Xe (8.9%) (could choose to later enrich/deplete)
- Exploit excellent self-shielding \rightarrow search in inner 11 tonne FV
- 10^7 reduction to detector centre
- XLZD $0\nu\beta\beta$ sensitivity paper: [J.Phys.G 52 \(2025\) 4, 045102](https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.10102)

Radiopurity and cleanliness

- Longer run time → ~ factor 3
- Critical materials scale with length² → factor 4
- **Largely mitigated by improved self-shielding → factor 1/10 with acceptable Xe-loss**

Challenge is for background sources that are poorly fiducialised:

- Rn-emanation ← important for low-energy signals (DM, solar- ν)
- High-energy gammas $^{238}\text{U}/^{232}\text{Th}$ decay chains ← important for $0\nu\beta\beta$

Fixed contaminants - U/Th/etc. in bulk material

Main driver → high energy gammas (from ^{214}Bi , ^{208}Tl in U/Th chains) → $0\nu\beta\beta$ ROI

Requires $O(10)$ $\mu\text{Bq/kg}$ sensitivity

- HPGe ($10 \mu\text{Bq/kg}$) - need factor 5 improvement
- ICP-MS (10^{-13} - $10^{-14} \text{g}_{\text{U/Th}}/\text{g}$) - factor 10 + throughput
- NAA ($10^{-14} \text{g}_{\text{U/Th}}/\text{g}$) - increase throughput with new facilities

+ Novel production low-bg materials:

- Electroformed Cu; 3D printed plastic components.

Fixed contaminants - α -n neutrons

- Neutrons from α -n reactions \rightarrow single scatter WIMP-like nuclear recoils
- Care about low-Z materials with high α -n cross sections (PTFE in particular)
- Mitigated via:
 - Control of material intrinsic contamination - typically sub-dominant to $0\nu\beta\beta$ requirements
 - Active veto system (with Gd-loading)
 - Vertex reconstruction \rightarrow exploit self-shielding of Xe, esp. Given larger detector volume

Radon emanation - need to be \ll Solar-PP

- Dominant background low-energy electron recoils
- Needs to be $\sim 0.1 \mu\text{Bq/kg}^*$ in Xe \rightarrow $O(10 \text{ mBq})$ absolute!
- Multi-pronged approach:
 - 1) Material selection \rightarrow ~ 5 - 10 improvement assay sens. ($100 \mu\text{Bq/m}^2$)
 - 2) Online distillation (c.f. XENONnT)
 - 3) Mitigation: barrier methods - e.g. electroplating critical components (cryostat, gas system); Improved analysis vetoes (larger detector).

<https://youtu.be/TdNQKASoT-U>

* c.f. LZ baseline $\sim 2 \mu\text{Bq/kg}$ and [0.9 \$\mu\text{Bq}\$ achieved by XENONnT with distillation column](#)

Radon emanation - flow tagging

- With fine control of circulation/Xe cooling → control Xe flow pattern
- Two flow states for 2024 data:
 - **High Mixing** - turbulent flow, uniform distribution of Rn & injected sources
 - **Low Mixing** - laminar-like flow, low-radon central region

[arxiv/2508.19117](https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.19117)

Radon emanation - flow tagging

- In low mixing state, use ^{222}Rn - ^{218}Po coincidences \rightarrow map liquid flow to efficiently tag ^{214}Pb β 's

Example neutral flow paths - 8-12 hrs

[arxiv/2508.19117](https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.19117)

Tag > 60% of decays with < 10% live-time hit -
and in reality still use the 10% in analysis

Cleanliness - dust and radon plateout

Surface contamination of detector materials during construction:

- Dust:
 - Radon emanation; alpha-n neutron production; ion recoils
 - Keep below 200-500 ng/cm² ← similar to current generation Xe-experiments
- Plate-out:
 - Implantation of radon progeny (²¹⁰Pb) during construction [0.2-0.5 mBq/m² required]
 - Neutron production from subsequent α decays → particularly care about PTFE, Al, etc.
 - Backgrounds from misconstructed decays on TPC walls → less important given larger TPC

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Control of surface contaminants

Building on well-developed protocols from the current gen (LZ, XENONnT):

- Extensive monitoring (UV inspections, Rn/dust counters, assays)
- Exposure tracking (witness plates/tape lifts, fallout/deposition models)
- Validated cleaning protocols (IPA, low-lint wipes, dry-ice/N₂ blast)
- LZ achieved:
 - Plate-out 160 $\mu\text{Bq}/\text{m}^2$ (req. 500)
 - Dust @ 200 ng/cm^2

In summary

- Ambitious plans for a 60-80 tonne LXe-based rare event search observatory
- Opportunity for broad DM and ν -physics programme
 - DM into the neutrino fog
 - Competitive $0\nu\beta\beta$ sensitivity
 - Solar, SN and other ν -searches
- Control of backgrounds is a key challenge
- Achievable building on track record/expertise from LZ/XENONnT

LZ UV dust inspection - credit LZ/Nicolas Angelides

